

A GROWING BACKLASH: QUANTIFYING THE EXPERIENCES OF LGBTQI+ PEOPLE, 2022-2024

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Executive Summary

⊕ LGBTQI+ human rights are deteriorating

Nearly two-thirds of countries experienced a decline in their scores on the F&M Global Barometers LGBTQI+ Perception Index™ (GBPI) from 2022 to 2024. The GBPI global average fell from a low 59 percent (F-Persecuting) in 2022 to an even lower 57 percent in 2024.

⊕ Backsliding on LGBTQI+ human rights is widespread

The region with the greatest number of countries whose overall GBPI score dropped between 2022 and 2024 is Western Europe, where 65 percent of countries experienced a decline; Western Europe is followed by the Americas, where 58 percent of countries experienced a decline in GBPI scores. This finding suggests that regression on LGBTQI+ human rights is occurring not only in politically unstable countries but also in established democracies with reasonably secure legal protections for LGBTQI+ people.

⊕ LGBTQI+ people feel less safe

A breakdown of the six questions on the 2022 and 2024 GBPI surveys shows that there was a significant decrease in scores on all questions between 2022 and 2024 except on Q5: Fear of Police. Q1: Safety and Q3: Acceptance fell by five percent, while Q2: Safety in Gathering had the greatest decline, seven percent.

⊕ Transgender women and intersex people feel least safe

In 2024, 36 percent of transgender women and 37 percent of individuals identifying as intersex reported feeling very unsafe or unsafe because of their gender identity or intersex status.

⊕ Transgender people are most likely to experience violence

Forty-three percent of transgender women and 40 percent of transgender men who completed the survey in 2024 reported that they were very likely or likely to experience violence because they were transgender.

Background

Although LGBTQI+ legislation is an important indicator of state support for the protection of LGBTQI+ people, it does not always translate into actual protections for LGBTQI+ people. The F&M Global Barometers LGBTQI+ Perception Index (GBPI) is a pioneering survey designed to measure LGBTQI+ individuals' lived human rights experiences. The GBPI was piloted in 2022 and launched again in 2024.

The first survey received over 170,000 responses, and the 2024 survey received just over 40,000 responses. Although there were some minimal changes to the wording of the questions from 2022 to 2024, both the 2022 and 2024 GBPI surveys focused on fundamental human rights (see **Table 1**).

Both surveys were anonymous and confidential and underwent human subjects research approval through Franklin & Marshall College. The data collected is not a representative sample of the worldwide LGBTQI+ population; however, it provides the best insight to date into the lived experiences of LGBTQ+ people worldwide.

Each country is assigned a letter grade (A to F, 0–100%) using a standardized grading scale (see **Figure 1**, below), where 100 percent (A) is the most positive and 0 percent (F) is the least positive.

Table 1. GBPI Survey Questions

Question 1 (Safety): How safe do you feel living as a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex person in your country?

Question 2 (Safety in Gathering): How safe do you feel gathering with other lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex people in public?

Question 3 (Acceptance): How accepted do you feel as a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex person by your society?

Question 4 (Discrimination): How frequently have you experienced discrimination in your day-to-day life because you are a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex person?

Question 5 (Fear of Police): How fearful are you of being arrested, harassed, or blackmailed by security forces/police because you are a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex person?

Question 6 (Violence): How likely are you to be a victim of violence because you are a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex person?

Figure 1. GBPI Grading Scale

In order to calculate each country's score, a weighted average is applied to the responses (Likert scale options 1–5) to arrive at a percentage. A response of “1” is equivalent to 0%; a response of “2” is equivalent to 25%; a response of “3” is equivalent to 50%; a response of “4” is equivalent to 75%; and a response of “5” is equivalent to 100%, with the number of responses that correspond to each percentage determining its weight. This process results in a final score between zero and 100 percent.

A complete summary of the F&M Global Barometers methodology for the GBPI and other barometers can be found in the [F&M Global Barometers Methodology Background Note No. 2](#).

To establish a comparative threshold, only countries with over 30 responses on the GBPI are counted toward analyses of the GBPI's results. A total of 118 countries recorded over 30 responses to the 2022 and the 2024 versions of the GBPI.

I. GLOBAL BACKSLIDING

Both the 2022 and the 2024 GBPI results reveal a disturbing reality for LGBTQI+ people. Although some countries may have robust human rights legislative protections for LGBTQI+ people, those legal protections do not always correspond to lived human rights experiences (see below, **Figures 2** and **3**).

In both the 2022 and the 2024 GBPI surveys, not a single country received a grade of A-Protecting. Only one country earned a B-Tolerant: Iceland. The majority of countries scored a grade of F-Persecuting. Perhaps not surprisingly, the regions with the lowest average scores were Central/Eastern Europe/Eurasia, Middle East/North Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa. The United States experienced a drop in average GBPI score from D-Intolerant (63%) in 2022 to F-Persecuting (58%) in 2024.

Figure 2. 2022 GBPI Global Results

Figure 3. 2024 GBPI Global Results

A. LGBTQI+ Human Rights are Regressing

The global GBPI average for 2024 was 57 percent, a two percent decline from the 2022 GBPI score (59%). Although both 2022 and 2024 global GBPI scores were in the F-Persecuting

category, a two percent drop globally signals widespread backsliding on LGBTQI+ human rights. Over two-thirds of countries experienced a decline in their overall GBPI score from 2022 to 2024, with scores decreasing in five of six regions of the world (see **Figure 4**, below).

Figure 4. GBPI 2022 & 2024 - Changes in Regional Scores

More specifically, scores for five of the six questions on the GBPI decreased between 2022 and 2024. This change suggests that human rights protections are becoming increasingly inaccessible for LGBTQI+ people, who disclosed feeling less safe and less accepted; experiencing more discrimination; and feeling more likely to be victims of violence (see below, **Figure 5**). Between 2022 and 2024, the greatest decline was reported in

Q2: Safety in Gathering, closely followed by Q1: Safety and Q3: Acceptance. If people feel less accepted, they would also feel less safe both individually and to gather with other LGBTQI+ people. Diminished feelings of safety and acceptance may also be a result of more frequent experiences with discrimination and violence, which inherently indicate decreasing state and societal tolerance for LGBTQI+ people.

Figure 5. GBPI 2022 & 2024 - Changes in Scores by Question

II. ESTABLISHED DEMOCRACIES ALSO EXPERIENCED REGRESSION

The F&M Global Barometer of Unified LGBT Rights™ (GBUR) tracks legislative protections and societal persecution for LGBT people in 204 countries and territories. While the expectation would be that countries with legislative protections would yield higher scores for perceptions of safety and safety in gathering, the difference between state protections and LGBTQI+ people's own experiences was made clear by the GBPI: Having access to LGBTQI+ legal rights protections did not guarantee that LGBTQI+ people actually felt protected.

Even countries scoring well on the GBUR are home to countless individuals who do not actually feel the impact of these laws in their lives. **Figure 6**, below, shows that only one region in the world earned a passing grade on

safety for LGBTQI+ people: Western Europe. Not only have perceptions of safety degraded in all regions between 2022 and 2024, but Western Europe, the highest-scoring region, earned only a D-Intolerant, or 63 percent, in 2024.

Just as perceptions of safety worsened among LGBTQI+ people on a global scale, there was a concomitant uptick in the likelihood of violence (or decrease in scores) on the GBPI between 2022 and 2024. Perceptions of victimization were measured by the GBPI question, "How likely are you to be a victim of violence because you are a lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and/or intersex?"

There was no improvement on violence scores in any region of the world between 2022 and 2024. While the Americas showed no change in its score of 53 percent between the two years, all other regions experienced a decline in scores ranging from one to 14 percent. **Figure 7**, below, depicts the regional scores for the perceived likelihood of experiencing violence.¹

Figure 6. GBPI 2022 & 2024 - Safety Scores by Region

Figure 7. GBPI 2022 & 2024 - Violence Scores by Region

III. TRANSGENDER WOMEN AND INTERSEX PEOPLE FEEL THE MOST UNSAFE

The GBPI results further illustrated that LGBTQI+ individuals did not perceive their safety as a homogenous group. Disaggregating safety scores by identity revealed varied experiences with safety among different LGBTQI+ identities. In fact, intersex individuals and transgender women recorded the most negative perceptions of their individual safety (responses of “Very unsafe” or “Unsafe”); while individuals self-identified as bisexual and gay reported the most positive perceptions of safety (responses of “Safe” or “Very safe”).

Figure 8, below, shows the global distribution of scores on the question of safety as they apply to individual LGBTQI+ identities.

Intersex individuals and transgender women reported feeling the least safe: thirty-seven percent of intersex respondents and thirty-six percent of transgender women reported feeling very unsafe or unsafe because of their intersex status or gender identity.

Transgender men and non-binary individuals reported the most ambiguity in their safety, with 44 percent and 40 percent of respondents in those identity groups, respectively, recording responses of “Somewhat safe.”

Figure 8. 2024 GBPI - Global Distribution of Safety Scores by Identity

IV. TRANSGENDER PEOPLE EXPERIENCE THE HIGHEST LIKELIHOOD OF VIOLENCE

The distribution of scores for Q6: Violence by identity produced a spectrum of experiences reported by LGBTQI+ individuals on the 2024 GBPI (see **Figure 9**, below). Transgender women and men reported the highest likelihood of experiencing violence.

Forty-three percent of transgender women responded “Very likely” or “Likely,” and 40 percent of transgender men responded “Very likely” or “Likely,” indicating these identity groups feel most at risk.

Conversely, a greater distribution of positive scores than negative were seen among bisexual, gay, lesbian, other, and queer respondents, illustrating that there are differences in experiences with violence among sexual orientation minorities compared to those of intersex individuals and gender identity minorities. Most notably, nearly half of bisexual and gay respondents indicated that they were unlikely or very unlikely to be victims of identity-based violence.

Over one-third of transgender men, non-binary, and queer respondents recorded feeling “Somewhat likely” to experience physical victimization, suggesting that these individuals do not feel secure against the threat of identity-based violence.

Figure 9. 2024 GBPI - Global Distribution of Violence Scores by Identity

V. VISIBILITY MATTERS

One indicator of how secure an individual feels with regard to human rights protections is how willing they are to make their identities visible to others. Ease of disclosing visibility is influenced by how safe and accepted they feel and by how often and to what extent they face discrimination. To measure visibility, the 2024 GBPI asked the question, “To what extent do you share your sexual orientation and/or gender identity with others?”

Western Europe and the Americas had the greatest levels of LGBTQI+ identity visibility, which coincides with the fact that many countries in the two regions have robust protections and national hate crime laws which protect both sexual orientation and gender identity minorities (see **Figure 10**, below).

Figure 10. 2024 GBPI - Visibility by Region

Of the 118 countries and territories that garnered more than 30 responses on the 2022 and 2024 GBPI, only 48 included sexual orientation in hate crime legislation by the end of 2024; 71 percent of these countries were from Western Europe or the Americas. Hate crime legislation for gender identity minorities was slower to improve, with only 36 of the 118 countries offering national protection; 81 percent of those countries were located in Western Europe or the Americas, as well.²

The incongruity between legislation and lived experiences was exemplified by three Western European countries – Germany, Iceland, and Ireland – all of which passed hate crime legislation protecting sexual orientation minorities between 2022 and 2024. Yet, all three countries showed a decrease in overall GBPI scores in 2024. This finding suggests that LGB individuals do not perceive their situations on the ground to be as rosy as legal protections would indicate. Their perceptions are informed by their experiences with violence and discrimination, which are shown to be on the rise worldwide.

VI. LGBTQI+ PEOPLE FEEL LESS SAFE TO GATHER

The GBPI also asked LGBTQI+ respondents to rate how safe they feel to gather with one another. The results from this question presented further evidence of worsening human rights conditions, with the global average for safety in gathering declining by seven percent between 2022 and 2024. The inverse relationship between violence and safety in gathering is shown in **Figure 11**, below.

Between 2020 and 2023, the number of countries with known acts of violence against LGBT people increased, while the number of countries allowing Pride events and reporting safe and peaceful assembly of LGBT organizations decreased simultaneously.³ Violence and the suppression of peaceful expression are clearly on the rise; the 2024 GBPI reflects that LGBTQI+ people's experiences with state and societal persecution are becoming more frequent in a majority of countries.

Figure 11. Relationship between Acts of Violence against LGBT People, State-Sanctioned Pride Events, & Peaceful Assembly

VII. CONCLUSION

The GBPI captures the human rights experiences of LGBTQI+ individuals. In 2024, GBPI respondents revealed that their perceptions of safety, safety in gathering, acceptance, discrimination, and the likelihood of violence have deteriorated compared to their answers to the same questions two years earlier.

Two-thirds of analyzed countries experienced regression in GBPI scores from 2022 to 2024. This finding suggests that the degradation in human rights experiences is widespread, affecting most countries, even those with established democracies.

Additionally, many respondents were hesitant to disclose their identities, possibly because of the fear of exposure or backlash.

Violence against LGBTQI+ people and the global decline in human rights protections underscore the importance of gathering firsthand accounts of these experiences.

The availability of future GBPI data will ensure that a fuller picture of the LGBTQI+ human rights landscape is available for activists, scholars, and policymakers. This data collection will also help ensure that LGBTQI+ voices are not silenced.

Notes

1. F&M Global Barometers, F&M Global Barometer of Unified LGBT Rights, 2011-2023, Dataset, Version 3, 2025, F&M Global Barometers, <https://www.fandmglobalbarometers.org/gbur-results>.
2. "Hate Crime Law," Legal Frameworks, SOGIESC Database, ILGA World, accessed November 10, 2025, <https://database.ilga.org/hate-crime-law-lgbti>.
3. F&M Global Barometer of Unified LGBT Rights, 2011-2023, <https://www.fandmglobalbarometers.org/gbur-results>.

About the Franklin & Marshall Global Barometers®

Since 2011, the Franklin & Marshall Global Barometers® (FMGB) have quantified global lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender (LGBT), and intersex human rights. The FMGB consist of four projects: the F&M Global Barometer of Gay Rights® (GBGR), the F&M Global Barometer of Transgender Rights™ (GBTR), the F&M Global Barometer of Unified LGBT Rights™ (GBUR), and the F&M Global Barometers LGBTQI+ Perception Index™ (GBPI). These four datasets track LGBT+ human rights and experiences in 192 UN member states and 12 additional territories or jurisdictions. The FMGB data provide a framework for accurately monitoring and analyzing the progression and regression of LGBT+ rights worldwide.

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